

ISic1174

Cadastral inscription for the territory of Halaesa

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

cadastral

Material

limestone (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 95 cm

Width 7 cm

Depth 61 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: b

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Fragment A

Column I:

(lines 1-2 too frag. for transl.)

...] descending along the boundary to the river[...] and descending along the river until [the rivulet

which borders] allotment 2, and upstream along the rivulet | | 5 [to the road] which leads to the

(spring) Ipyrra; the olives [which have been marked] at this point belong to this allotment. [The

land(?)] below the aqueduct as far as the Ipyrra spring shall not be worked, and the surrounding

space for 70 feet in every direction will be left free, but the trees will be harvested. | | 10

(Section 5) From the boundary marker at the Ipyrra spring, down along the road to the stunted olive,

on which is a boundary mark, and to the olive on which is a boundary marker, and by the road to the river and down along the river to the boundary of allotment 4, and along the boundaries of allotment 4; the olives which are marked here belong to this allotment. || 15 From the road which leads outside the city land, down along the road which passes the Meilichios sanctuary to the rivulet and down along the rivulet to the confluence of the rivulet and up along the rivulet to the road which leads outside the city land; to this plot belongs the water from the spring and the run-off from the bath.

|| 20 (Section 7) From the boundary of allotment 7 down along the road which leads towards the

Tapanon (a fortress?) to the ditch which borders the Themateitis (a sanctuary? a spring? a road?)

and where the ditches border the area (or garden) to the olive tree on which is a boundary marker,

and to the olive tree on which is a boundary marker, and to the rivulet, and up along the rivulet to

the road which leads towards the Tapanon; the olives which || 25 have been marked at this point

belong to this allotment. (Section 8) From the ditch which borders the Themateitis to the rill, and

down along the rill to the wild olive on which is a boundary mark, and turning about to the olive on

which is a boundary mark, and to the olive on which is a boundary mark, and to the olive on which is

a boundary mark, and to the olive || 30 on which is a boundary mark and to the stone on which is a

boundary mark, and to the olive on which is a boundary mark, and to the ditch, and to the boundary

marker at the Ipyrra (spring), and up along the road as far as the rivulet, and up along the rivulet

as far as the olive which has been marked, and along the boundaries of allotment 7; the olives which

have been marked at this point belong || 35 to this allotment.

(Section 9) From the wild olive on which is a boundary mark, and down along the rill to the olive on

which is a boundary mark, and to the olive on which is a boundary mark, and to the olive on which is

written (monogram Πό(λις) Ἀ(λαισίλων) ?), and where the ditches

border the pales, and down along
where there are the ditches and the pales as far as the barn
(taverna? cattleshed? masonry
building?) ||40 and from the barn up along the wall, and along the
wall to the ditch, and along the
ditches to the boundary marker which is over the road, and up
along the road to the boundary marker
which is at the Ipyrra (spring) and along the boundaries of allotment
8; the barn is shared in
proportion to that for which allotment 10 has been leased; the olives
which are marked ||45 at this
point belong to this allotment.
(Section 10) From the barn downwards where the ditches and the
pales are to the wall, and where the
wall is to the ditch and where the ditches are to the river and along
the river as far as the road
which borders allotment 5 and ||50 along the boundaries of
allotments 5 and 9. (Section 11) From the
boundary of allotment 7 down along the road which goes toward
the Tapanon to the highest corner of
the circuit wall of the Tapanon, and from the Tapanon down along
the approach road which leads to
the Adranieion, to the olive on which is a marker, and to the
pomegranate trees, and ||55 to the
olive on which is a marker, and along the ditches which are below
the boundary marker as far as the
rivulet and up along the rivulet to the ditch besides the Themateitis
and to the road which leads
towards the Tapanon; the olives which have been inscribed belong
to this allotment. (Section 12)
From the Tapanon down along the road as far as the rivulet, and
down along ||60 the rivulet as far
as the pale which border the rivulet and where the pales are as far
as the boundary of allotment 11,
and along the boundaries of allotment 11. (The lessee) will provide a
six-foot approach road to the
Adranieion and will keep a distance of 20 feet away from the temple
on all sides.
(Section 13) From the ditch which borders the (river) Opikanos down
along the Opikanos ||65 to the
river and down along the river as far down as the boundary marker
which is in the allotment and up

along the boundary markers to the marker which is by the fig-tree below the road and where the road is as far as the boundary of allotment 13, that of the large coppice, and such is the boundary of allotment 13, that of the large coppice. Double-allotment of the olive-yard || 70 Contents (lit: 'circumference'): any sacred (olive) belongs to the olive-yard; those who have leased the olive-yard shall not make a tannery or a cookhouse.

Column II:

(Section 11) [first six lines are fragmentary, only surviving at right margin] ... and ... which is below the ... to the boundary marker ... the boundary of allotment 9 and || 5 ... down along the river Opikanos ... and to the boundary marker, and to the ditch which borders [...?...] and where the boundary marker is and the ditches to the olive [on which is a boundary mark, and] to the boundary of allotment 10 and up along the boundary of allotment 10 as far as the boundary of the Pikattos and along the boundaries of the || 10 Pikattos; to this allotment belong the olives here which have been marked.

(Section 12) From the boundary marker below the Aspis to the Platamos (?flat rock?) where there is a boundary marker, and to the olive on which is a boundary mark, and to the ditch, and where the ditches are to the olive on which is a boundary mark, and to the road || 15 which leads from the Tapanon and up along the road as far as the boundary of allotment 7 and along the boundaries of allotment 7 to the boundary marker, and where the boundary marker is as far down as the Platamos; the olives marked here belong to this allotment.

(Section 13) From the boundary of allotment 11 down along the Opikanos to the ditch || 20 which borders the Opikanos and where the ditches are below the boundary marker to the road which leads to the Tapanon and up along the road as far as the boundary of allotment 12 and along the boundaries of allotment 12.

To those (living) along the river Halaisos (we have assigned) [7] allotments/divisions (as follows):

(Section 1) From the river Halaisos to the boundary marker on the rock which is beside the | | 25

tubs, and up along the ridge to the rock on which is a boundary mark, and to the road, up along the

road to the rill and up along the rill to the ditch which is below the boundary marker, and where

the boundary marker is beyond the ditch as far as the area (? garden), and above the garden where the

boundary marker is beyond the ditch and to the ditch which is beside the olive and beyond | | 30 the

olive where the beaten track is and the ditches to the olive on which is marked (monogram Πό(λις)

Ἀ(λαισίων)) and from the olive where the boundary marker is above the olive to the ditch and

upwards to the thorn bushes and where the thorn bushes are round the boundary marker and to the

ditch and upwards to the boundary mark on the stone and where the boundary mark is below | | 35 the

area (?garden) and to the boundary mark on the circuit wall and along under the wall to the rill

which is below the culvert in the wall where there is a boundary mark, and down along the rill to

the river Halaisos and up along the Halaisos to the beginning of the circuit (or delimitation). In

this (allotment is the land) of Agrios.

(Section 2) From the culvert in the wall where there is a boundary mark along beneath the wall as

far | | 40 as the boundary mark on the wall and from the boundary mark downwards where the ditches are

to the wild pear tree marked with (monogram Πό(λις) Ἀ(λαισίων)), and where the ditches are to the

olive marked with (monogram Πό(λις) Ἀ(λαισίων)), and to the fig tree marked with (monogram Πό(λις)

Ἀ(λαισίων)), and where the ditches are as far as the boundary marker and where the boundary marker

is to the rivulet and down along the | | 45 rivulet to the river Halaisos and up along the Halaisos to

the boundary of allotment 1; in this (allotment is land) of Elapheus.

(Section 3) From the boundary mark on the wall limiting allotment 2 as far as the rill flowing from

the sluice-gate (? - διαπαυμα) and down along the rill to the confluence of the rivulet and up along the || 50 rivulet to the boundary marker and along the boundaries of allotment 2; in this (allotment is land) of Elapheus.

(Section 4) From the rill (which flows) out of the sluice gate, along below the wall as far as the rill which flows out of the culvert below the temple, where there is the forge (?) below the cookshop (??), and down along || 55 the rill as far as the boundary marker where there is a ditch, and where the boundary marker is as far as the rill which flows from the sluice-gate bordering allotment 3.

(Section 5) From the boundary marker where the ditch is, down along the rill to the ditch and where the ditches are to the river Halaisos and up along || 60 the Halaisos as far as the rill which borders allotment 2 and up along the rill as far as the boundary marker which delimits allotment 4.

(Section 6) From the culvert below the temple of Apollo, below the forge(?) next to the cookshop(?) along beneath the wall as far || 65 as the culvert nearest to the little turret and down along the ridge where the ditches are to the area (or garden) and to the boundary marker and downwards where the ditches are to the boundary marker and where the boundary marker is and the ditches to the second rill and down along the rill to the river Halaisos and up along the Halaisos to the || 70 boundary of allotment 5.

(Section 7) From the wall down along the stream to the river Halaisos and up along the Halaisos as far as the first rill and up along the rill as far as the wall; in this (allotment is land) of Herakleides son of Apollonios and (land) of Philoxenos son of Meniskos.

|| 75 To the Skureonoi (we have assigned) 10 allotments (as follows):

(Allotment 1) From the culvert along the wall(?) as far as the culvert next to the second little turret and from the culvert down along the rivulet as far as the

boundary marker and where the
boundary marker is beyond the area (?garden) and up along the
ridge where the ditches are to the
culvert; in this (allotment is land) of || 80 Histieios son of Theston
and (land) of Pelagios.
(Allotment 2) From the boundary marker down along the rill as far
as the boundary marker, where
there is a ditch, and by the boundary as far as the rivulet which
flows along the space between the
soils(?) and up along the rivulet as far as the boundary marker and
where the boundary marker is to
the rivulet.
|| 85 (Allotment 3) From the boundary marker down along the
rivulet which runs in the space between
the soils(?) as far as the boundary marker where there is a ditch,
and where the boundary marker is
and the ditches up along the ridge to the boundary marker and
beyond the area (?garden), and to the
boundary marker, and where the boundary is as far as the rill.

Commentary

The translation of Fragment A is based upon the text of Dubois, IGDS no.196.

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.
At 14.0352 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1098

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 58.1039

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 56.1084

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 53.0997
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0917
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1191
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 48.1240
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1363
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1342
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.0844
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 40.0796
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 39.0991
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0929
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 37.0758
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0935
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 28.0763
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0045
undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1980.0592
Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 196 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)
Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliae objacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.182 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/310953>)
Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1753. Storia di Alesa, antica città di Sicilia. Palermo. At 153
Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio. Panormus. At cl.8 no.9
Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et

- notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata. Palermo.
At cl.8 no.11
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5594
- Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. *Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften*. Göttingen. At 5200
- Di Giovanni, V. 1885. La tavola alesina scoperta nel sec. XVI e il frammento trovato nel 1885. *ASS*. 10: 123-219.
- Sicca, U. 1924. *Grammatica delle iscrizioni doriche della Sicilia*. Arpino. At 211-231
- Manganaro, G. 1980. La provincia Romana. In Gabba, E., Vallet, G.(eds.), *La Sicilia antica*. Naples. pp. 415-461. At 430-435
- Ghinatti, F. 1993. Autenticazione e alienazione dei simboli. *Sileno*. 19: 39-70. At 54
- Ghinatti, F. 1996. *Assemblee greche d'Occidente*. Turin. At 48-50
- Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M. 1999. Le Tabulae Halaesinae: alcuni aspetti grafici e linguistici. In Gulletta, M.I.(eds.), *Sicilia Epigraphica*. Pisa. pp. 449-463.
- Scibona, G. 2002. Due note a IG XIV 352. *Tyche*. 17: 159-164.
- Corsaro, M. 2003. Ambiente e paesaggio in Magna Grecia: le fonti epigrafiche. *Ambiente e paesaggio nella Magna Grecia. Atti del quarantaduesimo convegno di studi sulla Magna Grecia. Taranto 5-8 ottobre 2002.* Taranto. pp. 133-167. At 156-159
- Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M. 2003. intervento. *Ambiente e paesaggio nella Magna Grecia. Atti del quarantaduesimo convegno di studi sulla Magna Grecia. Taranto 5-8 ottobre 2002.* Taranto. pp. 171-178.
- Scibona, G. 2003. Due note a I.G. XIV 352. In Fiorentini, G., Caltabiano, M., Calderone, A.(eds.), *Archeologia del Mediterraneo: studi in onore di Ernesto di Miro*. Rome. pp. 599-603.
- Facella, A. 2006. Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica. Pisa. At 115 n.153
- Cusumano, N. 2008. Culti e miti. *Kokalos*. 47-48: 443-62. At 456-460
- Manganaro, G. 2009. Il paesaggio agrario di Halaesa Archonidea. *Epigraphica*. 71: 9-28.
- Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M., Facella, A. 2012. Tusa. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G. (eds.), *Bibliografia Topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle isole tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 251-311. At 265-267

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